

Hi

It's hard to believe, but it's already been six months since we started HumanTech!

Through this ambitious and innovative EU-funded initiative, we are addressing the most critical challenges facing the European construction industry today. Our aim is to create a safer, greener, more efficient and rewarding industry for a new generation of highly skilled workers. How? By achieving major breakthroughs in cutting-edge technologies with a human-centred design.

If I had to highlight three things that [our team](#), made up of experts from 22 organisations in 10 countries, has made progress on in this period, they would be:

- **[We have started our field activities](#)** by collecting a large-scale multisensory building 3D point cloud dataset.
- **[We have gained recognition for our research](#)**, receiving awards at the [European Computer Vision Conference \(ECCV\)](#) and the [Best Paper Award at the European Council on Computing in Construction \(EC³\)](#).
- **[We have participated in our first events and made our first media appearances](#)**, which has allowed us to disseminate our work to a broader public.

What's next? In the coming months, we will continue to work on our technical work packages for the generation of digital building twins, construction wearables and robotics. We look forward to making some of our newly acquired building data available to the scientific community.

We are also very excited to organise a workshop at the [European Robotics Forum \(ERF\)](#) with two other Horizon Europe projects in the field of construction, [RobetArme](#) and [Beeyonders](#), in March 2023.

We are very much looking forward to what's to come and want you to be part of it.

Are you involved in an initiative related to HumanTech's mission and want to explore collaboration opportunities with us? We're all ears!

Jason Rambach,
HumanTech's Project Coordinator

Let's connect

From the HumanTech team, we wish you a wonderful holiday season and a peaceful and prosperous New Year!

Happy Holidays from everyone at
HumanTech!

In this newsletter, we're sharing the latest news related to HumanTech, as well as important updates, resources, opportunities to take action and inspiration about the construction sector. Hope you enjoy!

HumanTech Stories

[The EBC in HumanTech](#)

“The European Builders Confederation (EBC) will be involved in the usability assessment of the impact of the identified technologies on construction SMEs, in promoting the awareness of such solutions and in developing a new approach to training for the upskilling of the current and future workforce. Moreover, thanks to its position, EBC will play a key role in the EU-wide dissemination of the main projects' findings in the European Construction community and in building partnerships and synergies with other relevant initiatives and projects.”

[Read the whole story](#)

[Researchers from RPTU win the Best Paper Award at EC³](#)

Our partners from the University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU) Fabian Kaufmann, Christian Glock, and Thomas Tschickardt received the Best Paper Award at the 2022 European Council on Computing in Construction (EC³) for their publication on ScaleBIM.

[HumanTech on the German radio with Fabian Kaufmann](#)

Our team member Fabian Kaufmann (RPTU) has explained our project on the German radio station Antenne Kaiserslautern. Listen to the short interview in German and read the transcript in English.

[Our first field activity: Multi-sensor data capturing](#)

HumanTech team members from Ricoh, Scaled Robotics, the Zurich University of Applied Sciences, and the University of Kaiserslautern-Landau have captured data in an former hospital in Germany to start building a unique multi-sensor dataset and develop a digital inventory.

[DFKI augmented vision researchers win 2 awards in Object Pose Estimation challenge \(BOP Challenge, ECCV\)](#)

HumanTech's Project Coordinator Jason Rambach, Yongzhi Su and Praveen Nathan, scientists at our partner organisation DFKI Augmented Vision Research Unit, have won two awards for their Object Pose Estimation method in the categories of “Overall Best Segmentation Method” and “Best BlenderProc-Trained Segmentation Method” in the prestigious BOP Challenge 2022.

[5 objectives to understand what HumanTech is all about](#)

From a new breed of digital twins to wearable solutions or autonomous demolition and construction site robots, these are the five specific scientific and technological objectives we are targeting at HumanTech.

Meet the #HumanTechTeam

- [Jason Rambach](#), HumanTech's Project Coordinator and a Senior Researcher and Team Leader in Spatial Sensing and Machine Perception at the German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence (DFKI).
- [Bharath Sankaran](#), CTO and Co-founder of Scaled Robotics, leading HumanTech's work package 3: Dynamic Semantic Digital Twin Generation.

- [Gabor Sziebig](#), Research Manager at SINTEF, leading HumanTech's work package 5: Construction Robotics and Human-Robot Collaboration.
- [Gloria Callinan](#), Project Support Officer at the Technological University of the Shannon, leading HumanTech's work package 6: Human Factors – Training and Usability Assessment
- [Fabian Kaufmann](#), Researcher at the University of Kaiserslautern-Landau, leading HumanTech's work package 7: Pilots, Evaluation and Validation.

In the coming months, we will continue to introduce the rest of our team members — stay tuned for our next interviews and newsletters!

Beyond HumanTech

[Support for the digitalisation of construction SMEs](#)

A website dedicated to supporting the digitalisation of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in construction has been launched by the European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). It acts as a one-stop-shop portal to access various services for SMEs in the construction sector — from a digital maturity analysis to an interactive handbook and in-depth trainings.

[White Paper: Ontologies and Digital Building Twins](#)

BIMprove, an H2020 project, has contributed to this insightful white paper, recently published by the [Sphere](#) H2020 project. It presents a review of existing ontologies in construction, showcasing the use cases of [BIM2TWIN](#), [COGITO](#), [BIM4EEB](#), [BIMERR](#) and [BIMprove](#) projects.

[Fostering the demand for a skilled labour force in the construction industry](#)

“The construction industry employs 13 million people across the EU27 and is a major driver of economic development. Unfortunately, it seems to be failing at attracting younger generations. Blerta Vula Rizvanolli, BUILD UP's Ambassador, expands on the 5 main reasons for this and gives some key points that the construction sector must address to meet the demand for skilled workers and solve this problem.”

Opportunities to Take Action

The H2020 project BUS-GoCircular is looking for mentors & mentees at the EU level with the support of the Architects' Council of Europe (ACE-CAE). Do you have experience in circular building design? [Register here to become a mentor](#) and [here to become a mentee](#) by the **31st of December, 2022**.

Our partner BAuA is organising the IEEE International Conference on Advanced Robotics and its Social Impacts (ARSO), to be held in Berlin (5-7 June 2023). [Submit your paper](#) by the **31st of January, 2023**. Contributions in the scope of HumanTech's robotic technologies are very welcome!

[Take part in this STAND4EU \(10 mins\) survey](#) to help identify and validate solutions against barriers to standardisation in research and industrial innovation! With your feedback, this Horizon EU project will develop an interface to facilitate the collection and exchange of information on barriers, solutions and best practices in standardisation. It will also highlight the needs and requirements of stakeholders and actors involved in the standardisation process.

Meet Other Inspiring Projects

[ASHVIN](#) is a 3-year European project developing a digital twin solution to boost the European construction industry. It has entered its final year, which means that its technology has been developed and is now being piloted at 10 demonstration sites. Its aim is to validate 10 digital twin tools they have developed and to assess how these make construction management safer and more efficient. [Subscribe to the project's newsletter](#) to find out more.

REINCARNATE is a 4-year European project aimed at developing the technical and social means to give new opportunities to buildings, construction products and materials – thus maximising their life cycle and determining if they are suitable for reuse. From Spain to Hong Kong – and from SMEs to non-profits –, their diverse group brings together strong expertise in innovation projects and represents all actors in the construction industry value chain. [Subscribe to their newsletter](#) to learn more.

To finish, a fun recommendation from our partners at the Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (BAuA)

[Qualityland: Visit Tomorrow, Today!](#)

“This audiobook is about a completely digitised society. So somehow, the HumanTech context in a broader sense. Very recommendable!”

Thanks for reading,
The HumanTech Team

[Get in touch](#)

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